

the size distribution of coke and not its reactivity that influences the conversion of carbon dioxide to carbon monoxide.

In agreement with the above reasoning, it has been found by us that densite, a German synthetic fuel, well-known for its performance in the cupola, has a higher reactivity towards carbon dioxide at 1000°C than either a typical Australian or Durham foundry coke (Table 1).

TABLE I. SPECIFIC GASIFICATION RATES $\times 10^4$ (G/G D.A.F./MIN) OF AUSTRALIAN, DURHAM AND DENSITE FOUNDRY COKES WITH CARBON DIOXIDE AT 1000°C

Coke	Burn-off		
	20%	40%	60%
Australian	12.9	15.1	13.5
Durham	6.8	7.3	7.3
Densite	11.5	15.0	24.0

The reaction was carried out** in a furnace, whose temperature was raised in nitrogen to and maintained at 1000°C by a temperature controller supplied by Ether Inc. The cokes were contained in a quartz bucket suspended from a calibrated copper-beryllium spiral. The nitrogen was replaced by carbon dioxide (purified of traces of oxygen by passing over platinised asbestos), and the contraction of the spiral measured using a cathetometer fitted with a telescopic objective. The rates of gasification were calculated from the weight loss vs. time curves. The rate of flow of carbon dioxide was kept constant during the runs.

The results given above are also in agreement with the findings of Hedden³, who has shown that a coke labelled as 'Special Foundry Coke' has a higher reactivity towards carbon dioxide than other metallurgical cokes.

The foregoing does not exclude the possibility that reactivity may be important under extreme conditions. The experimental results of Blayden, Noble and Riley⁴, do show evidence of higher hearth temperatures when highly graphitised, and presumably, therefore, very unreactive materials, such as electrode carbon, are used in cupolas. On the other hand, Worner and Evans⁵, and Higgins and Kennedy⁶ find that in a cupola highly reactive carbonised brown-coal briquettes fail to achieve metal temperatures comparable to those obtained with German metallurgical cokes under the same conditions.

However, such extreme cases apart, the above considerations lead to the conclusions, that with metallurgical cokes such as are normally used in practice, reactivity has no major direct influence on the efficiency of cupola operation.

** The work was carried out whilst the author was a Senior Research Officer (Fellow) at the Mineral Chemistry Division of Coal Research, C.S.I.R.O., Chatswood, N.S.W.

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Differential Thermal Analysis of Some Fluoroberyllates

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THERMAL decomposition of sulphates has been investigated^{1,2}. Little seems to have been done on the thermal decomposition of fluoroberyllates. Since chemically they are similar it would be interesting to investigate the thermal decomposition of the fluoroberyllates. The following salts were taken for analysis:

(a) Copper fluoroberyllate, (b) Nickel fluoroberyllate, (c) Cobalt fluoroberyllate, (d) Potassium fluoroberyllate, (e) Aniline Fluoroberyllate.

All the metal fluoroberyllates contain water of crystallisation which are given up on heating. The aniline fluoroberyllate probably decomposes forming CO_2 , H_2O , HF and BeF_2 .

It was previously ascertained that hydrofluoric acid is not evolved when these salts are heated below 200°C.

Experimental

Apparatus used was a Deltatherm Model D200 (Philips Electronics Instruments Company). Heating rates varied from 2°/min to 16.75°/min. All runs were on samples (100–150 mg) against alumina as reference. The sample and reference material were contained in platinum crucibles (8 mm diam \times 10 mm depth) with a central recess.

The sample temperature (T) was measured from the sample thermocouple.

Preparation of metal fluoroberyllates: The metal fluoroberyllates were prepared by dissolving the respective carbonates in calculated amounts of fluoroberyllic acid. The solutions were filtered and kept in vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid and allowed to crystallise. The crystals were filtered off into sintered porcelain crucibles, washed twice with ice-cold water and once with 95% ethyl alcohol. After air drying for several hours the crystals were ground to fine powder and were then ready for use.

Aniline fluoroberyllate: Calculated amounts of fluoroberyllic acid and distilled aniline were mixed together and the resultant solution was evaporated in vacuum desiccator. The crystals obtained were redissolved in water. On adding alcohol to the aqueous solution colourless crystals of aniline fluoroberyllate separated.

Fig. 1

Results and Discussion

The D.T.A. curves (Fig. 1) of the metal fluoroberyllate hydrates indicate only one endothermic peak below 150°C, which may be attributed to both fusion and dehydration.

At temperatures above 150°C the decomposition reaction involved such a small enthalpic change that no peaks are evident. It should be noted that all the four curves of the metal fluoroberyllate hydrates are similar to each other.

To quantitatively define the peak a shape index S has been proposed³ from which the apparent order of the reaction can be calculated. The apparent order varied from 0.96 to 1.7.

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